

DISCRETE-EVENT SIMULATION RANKING OF GOODS AND SERVICES IN SYSTEMS OF E-COMMERCE

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Annotation: *Practical aspects of modeling are investigated algorithms and methods of ranking in e-commerce systems. An algorithmically optimal way to generate events for simulation of buy/sell events. Showing how to use data structures to obtain the optimal implementation of algorithms ranking.*

Keywords: *event modeling, ranking, algorithms and data structures.*

E-commerce systems occupy a significant place in world trade. So, according to the statistics of 2015 in developed countries e-commerce accounts for more than 10% of the total turnover and continues to grow steadily. As it grows, so does the need business in quality tools and open new frontiers in areas of logistics, speed and quality of customer service, ease of entry into the ranks of sellers, diversity of goods.

Ranking of goods and services is an integral part modern e-commerce systems. There are many variations of ranking methods that are based on different assumptions, but not all of them are equally good. We present a series criteria, compliance with which is mandatory for quality implementation of the ranking algorithm:

1. Non-aging.
2. Smoothness.
3. Lack of a priori information about the distribution of popularity goods.
4. Justice.

The following will provide more detailed information on each of the proposed criteria with justification of its necessity.

Non-aging

Timelessness is an important property of the ranking algorithm, consisting in the fact that with a complete stop of sales (due to technical or

for a real reason) the values of the product popularity rank should remain unchanged. However, a complete halt in sales may influence how the prices of goods will change after the resumption sales - for example, increasing the jumps in the market after the fact of the sale.

Smoothness

The smoothness criterion is responsible for the monotonic and smooth increase Popularity rank of a product in case of no sales for this product specific product and the presence of typical selling activity in general. A demonstration of the smoothness criterion can be seen in Figure 1. On this graph shows how the product gradually, smoothly and continuously loses popularity without sales. The facts of sales at the same time look as sharp jumps in popularity for the better.

Lack of a priori information about the distribution product popularity

Lack of a priori information about the distribution of popularity goods limits the possibility of knowledge about the distribution of real data captured in the ranking algorithm. The absence of such information is more likely to allow the algorithm to adapt to deviations that inevitably occur in real data. Others In words, this criterion can be formulated as a preference non-parametric methods and parametric formulations.

Justice

Fairness can be called the property of the algorithm to rank products with higher sales are generally higher. Given property of the algorithm cannot be called objective, since there are no unambiguous method of comparing the sales of goods, and it will acquire certain features depending on the applied evaluation method sales.

Figure 1. Graph of Amazon Sales rank versus time rank using the example of a product from the section eBooks. Compiled by the author based on.

Modeling of ranking algorithms.

The task of modeling the ranking algorithm is reduced to modeling of two processes: the sales process and the ranking. To model the sales process, information about typical distribution of popularity of goods and

services. According to study, the real distribution of sales of various categories goods on the Amazon website as a first approximation is described Zipfa distribution with an exponent close to unity. Sales Process for a single product is well described by the Poisson process with mathematical expectation equal to the value of popularity goods.

Modeling an array of independent Poisson processes can be done efficiently as follows. In data structure "heap" will store the times of sales start events for of each product placed there at the start of the algorithm, with the key to calculate the minimum in the heap will be the scheduled time sales. At each simulation step, a fact is extracted from the heap sales with minimum time, and the following fact is placed there sales for the retrieved item. Time of next sale calculated randomly based on the distribution inter-event interval for the Poisson process, which is exponential distribution with exponent, inversely proportional to the expected popularity of the sale. Further the process is repeated from the extraction step. Algorithmic complexity such a simulation is $O(M \log N)$, where M is the number simulated events, and N is the total number of goods

The modeling of the ranking algorithm itself depends on how what class does it belong to: to the class of dynamic (i.e. with the ability to receive an updated product rank immediately after processing algorithm of the fact of sale), or to the class of static (when possible only receiving all the ranks of goods at once at a fixed moment time)

Efficient simulation of dynamic algorithms is possible using the "skip list" data structure, whose implementation must support the RANK operation, returning the rank of the object (position in the sorted by criterion ranking list). The algorithmic complexity of such an implementation will be $O((K + M) \log N)$, where K is the number of requests per rank a specific product ($K = kN$ when receiving the ranks of all goods k times), M is the number of ranking indicator updates, and N is quantity of all goods.

Static ranking methods that can receive ranked list only at once for all products profitable model directly by sorting all products by ranking index. The algorithmic complexity of such simulation will be $O(k N \log N)$, where k is the number of samples ranking result, N is the number of all goods.

To calculate ranking metrics that are based on the number of sales in a fixed time window can be used the following algorithm providing $O(1)$ complexity in terms of one sale event. Let the data structure "deck" (deque) store the sequence of sale events in the order they appear, and product associated with it, and a separate associative array stores the number of events in the deck for each product. When a new event, we put it in the queue, while increasing the counter events for the corresponding product, and then we extract from the other end event queue until the time difference

between the new and retrieved event is no longer greater than the length of the fixed time window of the algorithm, simultaneously decreasing the event counters for products associated with the retrieved events. Thus, the queue will consist only of events that occurred in the us time window, and the array of event counters will contain up-to-date data after each new event.

REFERENCES:

1. Khavanova N.V., Bokareva E.V. Analysis of the global and Russian market e-commerce: trends and development problems // Service in Russia and abroad. 2017. No. 3 (73).

1. Access mode: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/analiz-mirovogo-i-rossiyskogo-rynka> elektronnoy-torgovli-tendentsii-i-problemy-azvitiya

2. [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.novelrank.com/>

3. Antipov E. A., Pokryshevskaya E. B. Rank-sales relationship in electronic commerce: Evidence from publicly available data on 11 product categories

4. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. - 2016. - T. 16. - S. 1-6.